

Presentation of focus groups

This document contains a brief description of each focus group. For details on how the focus group discussions were carried out, see MIGNEX Handbook Chapters 8 and 11:

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For the focus group data, see separate Zenodo record.

Focus group AFG1-A

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Shahrake Jabrael, Afghanistan, in July 2021. All those women were migrants in Iran along with their families more than 10 years ago. The age range for these participants was 23 – 38. The participants were educated at bachelor's degree except two of them who studied until the higher school degrees. Two of them were household wives, two were teachers, and one of them was a student. While the last one was a cloth designer. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Najia Alizada. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG1-B

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Shahrake Jabrael, Afghanistan, in July 2021. All the participants had a weak link with migration to outsider countries. While all of them were internally displaced people. The age range for them was 25-38. Four of the participants were either uneducated or completed primary schools while two of them were educated at bachelor's degrees. The participants in this focus group were mainly housewives, a university student, and a teacher. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Najia Alizada. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG1-C

This focus group discussion was held with seven men in Shahrake Jabrael, Afghanistan in July 2021. All FGD participants had strong links with migration. The age range for this FGD was 20 – 34 and most of them were educated at the university degrees, and two had completed secondary. All of them worked in different sectors except one of them who was jobless. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Najia Alizada and Ibrahim Ramazani. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG1-D

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Shahrake Jabrael, Afghanistan, in July 2021. The FGD participants had a weak link with migration and none of them have experienced it directly. The age range for this discussion was 22 – 33 and three of them were educated at higher school degrees, including one who had a bachelor's degree. Two of the participants worked for either daily wages or shop keeping, while the other two were jobless. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Najia Alizada and Ibrahim Ramazani. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG2-A

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Behsud district, Afghanistan, in July 2021. The women had weak migration ties and their close family members had not experienced migration. Five of the women were young, between 20-25, and one woman was in her thirties. Five of the participants were educated and had graduated from universities, one is a civil activist and another a teacher in private schools. While one woman was uneducated and a housewife. The discussion was held in Pashtu and moderated by Tahmina Akakhil. It lasted approximately 3 hours and 15 minutes and was audio-recorded. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG2-B

This focus group discussion was held with four women in Behsud district, Afghanistan, in July 2021. The participants themselves and their close family members experienced migration. The participants were of different ages, three of them were between 18-29 and one of them was in her thirties. Three participants were educated and one of them was uneducated. The discussion was held in Pashtu and moderated by Tahmina Akakhil. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 14 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG2-C

This focus group discussion was held with eight men in Behsud district, Afghanistan, in July 2021. The participants themselves or their close family members have experienced migration, six of the participants were between 18-29 and two of them were between 30-39, and they were all educated except one of them who was farmer, the discussion was held in Pashtu and moderated by Jawid Hussanzai. It lasted approximately one hour and 49 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG2-D

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Behsud district, Afghanistan, in July 2021. The participants themselves and their close family members have not experienced migration. The participants were mostly between 20-29 years old, and they were all students in universities except one of them who was a lecturer between 30-39 years old. The discussion was held in Pashtu and moderated by Jawid Hussanzai. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG3-A

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Shahrake Mahdia, Afghanistan, in June 2021. All participants have either experienced migration abroad or currently have immediate family members in foreign countries as migrants. The age range for these FGD participant is 20-29 years old. One of the participants has completed secondary school, while the others were university students. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Nassim Majidi and Zabihullah Barakzai. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 50 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG3-B

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Shahrake Mahdia, Afghanistan, in June 2021. All participants have experienced migration directly. In addition, currently they have immediate family members in Turkey, EU countries and USA. They are all household wives and beside home chores they do some handicrafts, carpet waving, and tailoring. The age range for these FGD participants was 20-39. The participants were mostly uneducated while one of them had passed primary and another had passed secondary school. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Nassim Majidi and Najia Alizada. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG3-C

This focus group discussion was held with four women in Shahrake Mahdia, Afghanistan, in June 2021. Neither the participants themselves nor their immediate family members have experienced any kind of migration abroad. They are at the age range of 21-31 and all of them are educated at school and university degrees. One of the participants does carpet waving, while the others include a housewife, student, and one who is jobless. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Nassim Majidi and Najia Alizada. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group AFG3-D

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Shahrake Mahdia, Afghanistan, in July 2021. The participants have a weak link with migration, and they did not experience any kind of migration abroad. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 39. They included a shopkeeper, a student, a teacher, and a man who is jobless. They were educated at high school, and one had received a bachelor's degree. The discussion was held in Dari and moderated by Najia Alizada and Zabihullah Barakzai. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV1-A

This focus group discussion was held with five women in São Nicolau, Cabo Verde, in February 2020. Members of the group had no immediate family members abroad and no personal experience of international migration. They were all in their 30s except one who was in her 20s. The participants were educated at secondary level or above and all worked in the public sector. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Celina Abreu. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV1-B

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Tarrafal, São Nicolau, Cabo Verde in February 2020. All participants had immediate family members abroad or personal migration experience, or both. For instance, one grew up abroad and was a teenager when his family returned; another had his parents abroad from he was an infant. They were in their 20s or 30s and all had post-secondary education. Three out of four worked in the private sector. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Celina Abreu. It lasted approximately 1 hour and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV1-C

This focus group discussion was held with four women in Vila da Ribeira Brava, São Nicolau, Cabo Verde, in February 2020. All had family members abroad and two had lived abroad. Their ages ranged from 18 to mid-30s. Two were unemployed, one was a civil servant, and one was a student. All except the youngest had some post-secondary education. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Celina Abreu. It lasted approximately 1 hour and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV1-D

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Vila da Ribeira Brava, São Nicolau, Cabo Verde, in February 2020. The participants did not have immediate family members abroad, nor personal migration experience. However, some had close family members who previously lived abroad. Their ages ranged from late teens to mid-30s; all had completed either primary or secondary school, but none had additional education. One was unemployed, one was a student, and the two others were independent professionals. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Celina Abreu. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV2-A

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Boa Vista, Cabo Verde, in March 2020. All participants had come to Boa Vista from other islands, in most cases more than a decade ago. They were currently in their 30s. Some had secondary and some had post-secondary education, and all worked full time in technical or administrative positions in the public or private sector. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Samira Vieira. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV2-B

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Boa Vista, Cabo Verde, in March 2020. All were natives of Boa Vista, aged in their 20s or 30s. Three out of four had post-secondary education and all worked in public administration or tourism. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Samira Vieira. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV2-C

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Boa Vista, Cabo Verde, in March 2020. All participants were Boa Vista natives, though one has lived for many years on another island before returning a couple of years ago. They were all in their 30s. Their levels of education ranged from primary to post-secondary. All worked full time in either the private or public sector. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Samira Vieira. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group CPV2-D

This focus group discussion was held with three women in Boa Vista, Cabo Verde, in March 2020. All were born and raised on other islands and moved to Boa Vista 10–15 years ago. They were all in their 30s, had post-secondary education and worked full time in the public or private sector. The discussion was held in Kriolu and moderated by Jørgen Carling and assisted by Samira Vieira. It lasted approximately 50 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH1-A

This focus group discussion was held with four women in Kombolcha, Ethiopia in June 2021. The group had no migration experience and no immediate family members abroad. All of the women were in their early to mid-twenties. Three of the women had some post-secondary education; the other had completed high school. All the women were unemployed except for one who owned a small business. The discussion was held in Amharic and moderated by Medareshaw Tafesse with Camille Kasavan in attendance. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH1-B

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Kombolcha, Ethiopia, in June 2021. None in the group had any direct migration experience and no one had immediate family abroad. The participants were mainly in their mid to late twenties, with two participants in their early thirties. All the participants were unemployed except for one who was self-employed. Two of them had only completed primary education, one had only completed high school and three had some post-secondary schooling. The discussion was held in Amharic and moderated by Medareshaw Tafesse with Camille Kasavan in attendance. It lasted approximately 2 hours and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH1-C

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Kombolcha Ethiopia, in June 2021. All the men had direct migration experience: two of them had migrated internally to Afar for at least two years, the other three had international migration experience to Kenya and Saudi Arabia. Most of the participants were in their early thirties, with one in his mid-twenties. Three of the participants had at least completed high school, and two had only completed primary school. Two were unemployed, and three worked as daily labourers in construction or a furniture shop. The discussion was held in Amharic and moderated by Medareshaw Tafesse with Camille Kasavan in attendance. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH1-D

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Kombolcha, Ethiopia in June 2021. All of the women had direct migration experience – three of them had spent at least two years in Saudi Arabia, and two of them in Dubai. Three of the women were in their mid to late thirties, and two were in their mid to late twenties. Three of the women had only completed primary school, one had completed high school, and one had some post-secondary experience. The discussion was held in Amharic and moderated by Medareshaw Tefesse with Camille Kasavan in attendance. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH2-A

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Batu, Ethiopia in June 2021. None of the men had any migration experience or any immediate or close family members abroad. All of the men were in their early to mid-20s. Most of the men had some post-secondary education; one of the men had only finished high school, and one had only completed primary school. The discussion was held in Amharic, with some interjections in Oromifa and moderated by Fahmi Mohammed, with Tewelde Adhanom and Camille Kasavan present. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH2-B

This focus group discussion was held with eight women in Batu, Ethiopia in June 2021. None of the women had any direct experience with migration or any family members abroad – they had all been born and raised in the research area. The women were all in their early to mid-20s. Half had completed at least high school, and the other half had some post-secondary education, with at least two college graduates. Many of the women worked in shops or had their own “bunna bet” (small coffee shop); two were unemployed and one was a student. The discussion was held in Amharic and moderated by Tewelde Adhanom, with Camille Kasavan also present. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 50 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH2-C

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Batu, Ethiopia, in June 2021. All of the participants had migration experience with migrating internally and had been gone for a minimum of three years. All had returned and were now living in Batu. All the participants were in their early to mid-20s. Three of the participants had at least attended some post-secondary education, one had finished high school. All were employed: one worked as a teacher, one for an NGO, and two in construction. The discussion was held in Amharic with some interjections in Oromifa and moderated by Tewelde Adhanom. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 45 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH2-D

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Batu, Ethiopia in June 2021. Three of the women had international migration experience to Gulf countries, two of them had internal migration experience of at least three years. All had returned to live in Batu. The women were all in their mid to late 20s. Two of the women had at least some post-secondary education, two had only completed primary school, and one had only completed high school. The discussion was held in Amharic and Oromifa and moderated by Tewelde Adhanom. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH3-A

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Moyale, Ethiopia in July 2021. The group had migration experience including two men with refugee status who had studied and worked in Nairobi for more than three years. Except one in his mid-30s, all of the men were in their mid-20s. Three of them had post-secondary education including college degrees, with one who had completed secondary school. One of the male participants was unemployed, whereas the others were self-employed, or employed through governmental and non-governmental organizations. The discussion was held in Oromifa and moderated by Abreham Alemu with Tewelde Adhanom attending. It lasted approximately 2 hours and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH3-B

This focus group discussion was held with five females in Moyale, Ethiopia, in July 2021. No one in the group had any direct migration experience and no one had immediate family abroad. All the participants were in their mid to late 20s. All of the participants were unemployed. All of them had post-secondary schooling, and some of them with college degrees. The discussion was held in Oromifa and moderated by Abreham Alemu with Tewelde Adhanom in attendance. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH3-C

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Moyale Ethiopia, in July 2021. None of the men had migration experience. Most of the participants were in their mid to late 20s and only one in his 30s. Two of the participants had completed high school, and four had post-secondary education. Three were unemployed, one worked as self-employed in transportation, one in a photo studio, and the last one was religion teacher. The discussion was held in Oromifa and moderated by Abreham Alemu with Tewelde Adhanom in attendance. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 50 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group ETH3-D

This focus group discussion was held with 5 women in Moyale, Ethiopia in July 2021. All of the women had direct migration experience with some of them very strong links – one of them had spent at least five years in Saudi Arabia and Nairobi, and two of them have experienced working in border town of Kenya, another one studied in Kenya border town and continuing her college degree in Nairobi. One of the participants was 18-19 years old, two of the women were in their late 20s and two were in their mid-30s. Three of the women had less than primary education, one had only completed primary school, and one had completed high school. The discussion was held in Oromifa and moderated by Abreham Alemu with Tewelde in attendance. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA1-A

This focus group discussion was held with thirteen women in Gbane, Ghana, in March 2020. All participants had weak links with migration. We operationalise weak links with migration as people who might have a family member who has ever migrated, but they themselves have no migration experience. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 39. Most of the group had not completed primary education and were not in paid employment outside of their household. One woman engaged in farming. The discussion was held in Talen and English and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin as researchers with the research assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima and Maurice Korah as interpreters. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 50 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA1-B

This focus group discussion was held with twelve women in Gbane, Ghana, in March 2020. All participants had strong links to migration, with all of them having migrated to Gbane from other regions in Ghana. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 39. The majority of participants had completed secondary education and were not engaged in paid employment outside of their household, apart from one teacher and one trader. The discussion was held in Talen and English and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin as researchers with the research assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima and Maurice Korah as interpreters. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA1-C

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Gbane, Ghana, in March 2020. All participants had weak links with migration. We operationalise weak links to migration to mean people who might or might not have a family member who has ever migrated but they themselves have no migration experience. The participants ranged in age between 20 and 39. They had all completed secondary education or beyond, and worked as farmers and teachers, aside from one who was unemployed. The discussion was held in Talen and English and moderated by Marie Godin and Theophilus Kwabena Abutima as researchers and Maurice Korah as interpreter. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded by means of notetaking. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA1-D

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Gbane, Ghana, in March 2020. All participants had worked for at least one year in another town or had moved to Gbane as a child. The participants ranged in age from 18-39. They had all attended primary school, and each now worked in both mining and farming. The discussion was held in Talen and English and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin as researchers with the research assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima and Maurice Korah as interpreters. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 50 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA2-A

This focus group discussion was held with eight women in Bethlehem/Golf city, Ghana, in July 2021. All the women in the FG had a connection with migration. Many of them had migrated for work to the Gulf countries (Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Lebanon) and came back due to the pandemic. One migrated to South Africa as a tourist and is the only one with a university degree. She also had connections with people in her family who had migrated to the US/UK. The majority are in their 20s with three of them in their 30s. The level of education was quite low with two who had only completed primary education and three who attended junior high school. Only two completed secondary high school and one had a university diploma. The discussion was held in English and Twe and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA2-B

This focus group discussion was held with eight men in Bethlehem/Golf city, Ghana, in July 2021. They all had a strong connection with migration either having migrated themselves (especially within Africa) or knowing someone in their family circle who has migrated (to the US/Europe). The participants were educated either having completed secondary level or above. Two were unemployed at the time of the FGD and the rest had a professional occupation. Three of the participants were involved into e-marketing (Q-Net), a new business initiative in the area. The discussion was held in English and a few occasions in Twe, it was moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA2-C

This focus group discussion was held with nine men in Bethlehem/Golf city, Ghana, in July 2021. They all had a weak connection with international migration but most of them had migrated internally. None of them were born in the area. Many were from the Volta Region. They also migrated around Golf city and Bethlehem to Tema/Ashaiman before moving to the research area. However, they had developed over time a sense of belonging to the place and considered themselves as locals. Six out of nine participants were over 30 and therefore the three youth (under 30) were a minority in this group. The discussion was held in English and a few occasions in Twe, it was moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima. It lasted approximately 1 hour and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA2-D

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in Golf city, Ghana in July 2022. None of the participants had ever migrated outside Ghana. Some had family members/acquaintances with an experience of international migration. The majority of them were in their 20s except two who were respectively 18 years old and 39 years old. The participants were educated at secondary level or above and four of them had a job at the time we conducted the FGD except two who were unemployed. The discussion was held in English and in Twe, it was moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Theophilus Kwabena Abutima. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA3-A

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in New Takoradi, Ghana, in December 2021. Strong links with migration were identified as having someone close to the person who migrated outside Ghana (brother/sister, mother/father, husband). All participants had close relatives abroad, though none of the women themselves had migrated. The majority, four out of seven, of the women who took part in the FGD were between 20 and 39 years old except one who was 19 years old. Their level of education was quite high but in Ghana the secondary system consists of Junior High School (3 years) and Senior High School (3 years). Two of them had completed Junior High School but not Senior High School. The majority of the women are traders with one exception that has a degree and is a Senior high school graduate teacher. The discussion was held in both English and Fanti and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Kingsley Baffoe and Kareb Ahli Edinam. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 34 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA3-B

This focus group discussion was held with six men in New Takoradi, Ghana, in December 2021. Strong links with migration were identified as those who have had an experience with migration (either through irregular and/or regular means). The participants were all in their mid to late 20s, with one in his early 20s and two in their 30s. In terms of education, the majority had completed secondary school, only one completed primary school only and one gained tertiary education after high school. All of them were working at the time of the FGD with half of them employed by local companies, one into the fishing business, one self-employed and two into local casual work. The discussion was held in English mainly and sometimes in Fanti and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Kingsley Baffoe and Karen Ahli Edinam. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA3-C

This focus group discussion was held with seven men in New Takoradi, Ghana, in December 2021. Most the participants had some connection with migration (such as having a brother living in Italy, an uncle in Spain or in Germany or a friend who had left to go to Europe) but they themselves had never migrated before. One of them was 19 years old, four were 23 years old, one was 27 and the last participant was 33 years old. In terms of education, three had reached Junior High School but not carried their studies further. Three others had completed Senior High School and one had gained tertiary education. The discussion was held in both English and Fanti and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Kingsley Baffoe and Karen Ahli Edinam. It lasted approximately 2 hours and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GHA3-D

This focus group discussion was held with nine women in New Takoradi, Ghana, in December 2021. The majority of them knew someone who had migrated. Six of them were in their 20s except one who was in her late 30s and two who were respectively 18 and 19 years old. Among the participants, four had completed senior high school and one who had completed tertiary education. Four had only completed Junior High School. In terms of activities, three mentioned that they were unemployed at the time of the discussion. One was a teacher at a primary school, four were traders (fish, water, plantain) and one was running a hairdressing business. The discussion was held in English and Fanti and moderated by Leander Kandilige and Marie Godin with the assistance of Kingsley Baffoe and Karen Ahli Edinam. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 45 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN1-A

This focus group discussion was held with five young men in Boffa, Guinea, in October 2021. The participants had all studied in Conakry but had decided to come back and settle in Boffa to contribute to the development of their locality and, hopefully, to start a career as social entrepreneurs and members of civil society. Thus, they advocate for the possibility of Guinean youth to succeed in their own countries and reject the idea of migration as a solution for their problems. All participants were in their mid-20s. The discussion was held in French (with some digression in Sosso) and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore, assisted by Ester Botta. It lasted approximately 2 hours (some of the time was spent on visiting premises and informal conversations). It was audio-recorded, transcribed in French, and translated to English. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN1-B

This focus group discussion was held with six men. The conversation took place in the village Douminyia in the town of Boffa, Guinea, in October 2021. They were Sosso and Baga craftsmen, except from one trader. The craftsmen had been or currently were very mobile as skilled craftsmen they had contracts in several towns and some of them had workshops in two different localities. Others had spent a part of their life elsewhere in Guinea, working as mechanics, plumbers, welders, electricians, or smiths, before deciding to come back to Boffa. They were all in their late 30s and they had attended school for a short time, or not at all. The discussion was held in Sosso and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore, assisted by Ester Botta. It lasted approximately 2 hours. The discussion was recorded, translated, and transcribed into French, then translated to English. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN1-C

This focus group discussion was held with five women. It was held in Boffa, Guinea in October 2021. Some of the women have moved to Boffa to follow their husbands, others have grown up in the area because their fathers were civil servants from Haute Guinée assigned to hospitals and schools in Boffa. The group was made by women of different statuses, ages, and social conditions. The women aged from 20 to 39. The group included a woman who had attended University, one who had finished high school, and three with less than primary education. Besides being active in local civil society groups, the participants are housewives and/or traders, and one primary school teacher. The discussion was held in Sosso and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore, assisted by Ester Botta. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was recorded, translated, and transcribed in French and then translated into English. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN1-D

This focus group discussion was held in Boffa, Guinea in October 2021, with four women. They had weak connections with migration, as they had spent all their life in Boffa, except for trips to Conakry to sell fish. The women who spoke were in their late 30s, without primary education, and mothers of several children. All the women sold fish. The discussion was held in Sosso and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was recorded, translated into French and transcribed, then translated into English. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN2-A

This focus group discussion was held with eight young men in Dialakoro, Guinea, in August 2021. Some of them had left Dialakoro for some years, to study or learn a trade in the main Guinean cities (Conakry, Kamsar, Kankan) but, unlike many people of their generation, they never lived abroad in neighbouring countries. They were young men from 20 to 35 years old, mostly married with children. Some of them had stable jobs as farmers or workers, but some others were just starting new entrepreneurial activities. Many were university graduates returning to the village, but there was also a farmer without primary education. The discussion was held in Maninka and French and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore, assisted by Ester Botta Sompore and by Dougo Kpakpavogu, who was also the interpreter. It lasted approximately 1 hour 30 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN2-B

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in Dialakoro, Guinea, in August 2021. All the women had spent some time outside Dialakoro, mainly for small scale gold mining, or to study in other towns where they have relatives, but none has been outside Guinea. All were very young from 18 to 24. They are all students: two in High School and five in Middle School. Four of them are also learning a trade in the afternoon. The discussion was held in Maninka and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore, assisted by Ester Botta and Dougo Kpakpavogui as an interpreter. It lasted approximately 1 hour and was audio recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN2-C

This focus group discussion was held with eight men in Dialakoro, Guinea, in August 2021. All the participants had travelled abroad to neighbouring countries, such as Mali, Senegal, Burkina Faso, Ghana and Ivory Coast, in general to look for gold and diamonds. All were aged 29-39. One of them was a teacher in primary school who had completed University. Except from a man who had attended High School, all the rest were without primary education or had only attended two or three years in primary school. Four of them were craftsmen, but there were also two farmers, a trader, and a teacher. Occasionally, two representatives from the local government entered the discussion with some personal observations. The discussion was held in Maninka and moderated by Abdoulaye Wotem Sompore and Dougo Kpakpavogui. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated in French and then in English. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

Focus group GIN2-D

This focus group discussion was held with eleven women in Dialakoro, Guinea, in August 2021. They had weak ties with migration as they had spent all or most of their life in Dialakoro and the immediate surroundings (except for a woman who grew up in Bamako and came back to Dialakoro for marriage) and are now living in the village. They do not have significant connections with migrants either. Most of the women were married housewives between 25 and 35 years old. They also do agriculture and one of them is a trader. Most do not have primary education, but two of them finished primary school and another one attended a vocational training institute in Kankan to become a health worker. The discussion was held in Maninka and moderated by Abdoulaye Sompore and the research assistant Dougo Kpakpavogui was the interpreter. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

NGA1-A

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Down Quarters, Nigeria, in October 2021. Four of the participants are first generation migrants while two are second generation migrants. Five of the participants were in their thirties while one was in her twenties. Two of them are Muslims while four are Christians. As per their level of education, two participants three of the participants had completed their primary education, two have completed secondary education while one has post-secondary school education. Three of the participants are engaged in petty trading mostly selling food items and clothing. Also, two of them are full time housewives and depend on their husbands for provision of basic amenities while one participant used to have a white-collar job but lost her job as a result of COVID-19. The discussion was held in in both Hausa and English language and moderated by Aisha Adamu who served as the interpreter. It lasted approximately about fifty minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded by means of note-taking. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

NGA1-B

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Down Quarters, Nigeria, in October 2021. Five of the participants are third generation migrants while one is a fourth-generation migrant. Two of the participants are in their thirties, two in their twenties while one is nineteen years old. All participants are Muslims from the Hausa ethnic group. As per their level of education, four participants have completed their primary education while two have completed secondary education. Two of the participants are engaged in petty trading mostly selling food items, two participants are full-time housewives and two participants are employed in a tailoring shop. The discussion was held in in Hausa language and moderated by Aisha Adamu who served as the interpreter. It lasted approximately about fifty minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded by means of note-taking. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

NGA1-C

This focus group discussion was held with eight men at the only primary school in Down Quarters, Kaduna Nigeria, and 31st October, 2021. While four of the participants are fourth generation migrants, the other four are third generation migrants. The participants consisted of five discussants in their thirties and three in their twenties. The majority of the discussants (6) are Muslims and only two are Christians. In terms of education, the discussants have all completed their secondary education, with two of them still in tertiary institutions. All of the participants, except one primary school teacher, are engaged in the informal sector practicing different forms of vocations ranging from petty trading, welder, driving, tailoring etc. Although the discussants claim to understand the English language they suggested that the conversation be held in Hausa language. However, in the course of the conversation a bit of English was introduced. The discussion was moderated by Amos James. He was assisted by Kamal Abubakar a lecturer with the Department of Sociology Kaduna State university who served as an interpreter and a note taker. The discussion lasted for about 1 hour, 40 minutes and was audio recorded. The audio recording was translated and transcribed afterwards. In the course of transcription, we ensured that the identity of the discussants were not disclosed.

NGA1-D

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Down Quarters, Nigeria, on 2nd November 2021. All the discussants only recently migrated to Down Quarters. None of them has lived in the community for more than ten years. Four of the respondents are within the age range of 19 to 27 years and two of the respondents are in their early thirties. While four of the discussants are Muslims, two are Christians. Out of the four who are Muslims two are from the Hausa ethnic groups, while one is from the Igala ethnic group, the other hails from the Yoruba ethnic group. Among the two Christian one is from the Igbo ethnic group and the other one is from the Atyap ethnic group from Southern Kaduna State. Their level of educational attainment revealed that five of the discussants have completed their secondary education only one is currently in a tertiary institution. It was similarly noted that out of the six discussants two of them, are unemployed, one is a petty trader, the other is a barber, another is motor mechanic and the last one is a carpenter. The discussion was largely held in Hausa language but a bit of English was also used by both the moderator and some of the discussants. Amos James served both as moderate as well as the interpreter. The conversation which lasted for about 1 hour and 12minutes was recorded, and the audio-recording was later translated and transcribed. However, it was ensured that transcribed report did not reveal the identity of the discussants. In addition to the audio recording the moderator took detailed notes of the entire conversation.

NGA2-A

This focus group discussion was held with eight women in Awe, Nigeria on the 2nd of November 2021. Of the eight participants three had family members in other parts of Nigeria, while five had migrated at different points in time into the location currently known as old Awe from other parts of Nigeria. From informal conversations it seemed that a number of the long-term residents into Old Awe had migrated from Katsina. The age composition of the group was from 18-39, they included 1 housewife, two farmers, 1 food vendor, 1 private school teacher, 1 hair weaver, 1 fisher woman and a cleaner at the health facility. Only a few of the participants had a formal education and most are self-employed. The discussion was held in Hausa language and was moderated by Esther Gbaden while Jacob Agwam assisted by taking notes. It lasted approximately 40 minutes and was audio recorded.

NGA2-B

The focus group discussion comprised eight women in Awe, Nigeria who had weak ties to migration. It was held on the 3rd of November 2021 in an open compound in Awe. The group composition varies along ethnic lines and also represented a variety of ages from age 18-39. A few out of the women were Tiv, others were Eggon and Koro and some were Hausa. None of the participants had migrated however three out of the women had a distant relative (not close family), friend or classmate who had migrated. Most women were not formally educated, they also were mostly engaged in petty trade and in the service industry. The discussion which lasted for an hour three minutes was held in English and moderated by Esther Gbaden while Jacob Agwam did the interpretation and John Ihuman took notes. The discussion was audio recorded.

NGA2-C

This focus group discussion was held with seven men in new Awe on 1st November 2021. Five of the participants were migrants from different parts of Nigeria. Only two participants had a family member who migrated out of Awe to another state. The farmer had a brother who migrated to Abuja and the teacher had a son who migrated to Taraba and was yet to return. The participants ranged from 18-39. They included a teacher, farmer, mason, taxi driver, fisherman, trader, and one unemployed person. The discussion was held in an open compound in Awe moderated by George Genyi with assistance from John Ihuman and Jacob Agwam as interpreter. The discussion lasted approximately 90 minutes and was audio-recorded.

NGA2-D

This focus group discussion was held with 8 men in new Awe on 3rd November 2021. All the participants have no personal experience with migration with and have no immediate family member who has migrated. The participants ranged in ages from 18-39. They included a teacher, farmers, civil servants, students, and a security guard. The discussion was held in an open compound in Awe moderated by George Genyi with assistance from John Ihuman and Jacob Agwam as interpreter. The discussion lasted approximately 1 hour and 45 minutes and was audio-recorded.

NGA3-A

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Ekpoma, Nigeria, in November 2021. The group had strong ties to international migration because all the members except one were returnees from Europe, Niger, Algeria and Libya. In addition to their experience, they had knowledge about the means and benefits of international migration, but felt they were constrained in actual departure by visa restrictions. They all had the intention to travel abroad to live there if the opportunity became available. The selection of group participants was done to ensure fair representation of persons between 18 and 39 years (39, 28, 26, 30, 27, 21). While three of the participants had university education, the other three had attended secondary school (high school). This differential level of education also reflected in the jobs they do presently. While those with higher education work in the public service, the three men with little education performed menial construction (bricklaying) and petty trade. However, all the participants were literate, hence the discussion was done in English. The focus group discussion was moderated by Dr Iro Aghedo and research assistant Uyi Abudu. It lasted about 35 minutes and was audio-recorded and transcribed. Information that could reveal the identity of the participants was removed.

NGA3-B

This focus group discussion was held with nine men in Ekpoma, Nigeria, in November 2021. The group had weak ties to international migration because all the members (except one) had not travelled abroad before. However, they were familiar with local campaigns against irregular migration and human trafficking. They had no intention to travel abroad because they had no means of raising the substantial money needed for regular and safe international migration. The selection of group participants was done to ensure fair representation of persons between 18 and 39 years (38, 19, 18, 26, 24, 39, 22, 25, 35). Five of the participants were petty traders. The other four participants included two farmers, a technician, and an unemployed person. Three of the participants had university education, four completed secondary school, while the other two participants had only primary education. However, all of them were familiar enough with the English language to allow discussion to be conducted in the same. The focus group discussion was moderated by Dr Iro Aghedo and research assistant Uyi Abudu. It lasted about 30 minutes and was audio-recorded and transcribed. Information that could reveal the identity of the participants was removed.

NGA3-C

This focus group discussion was held with 8 women in Ekpoma, Nigeria, in November 2021. The group has strong ties to international migration; while some are returnees from Europe, others desire to Europe and North Africa, and other West African countries like Senegal, Mali, Ivory Coast, and Ghana. Many go to North African countries like Libya with the aim of arriving in European countries like Italy and Spain. and have good knowledge of the routes, means and connections to international migration, although through irregular means on vehicles through the Sahara Desert and using inflatable boats on the Mediterranean Sea. Participants were selected between the age ranges of 18-39 (18, 19, 21, 24, 25, 34, 35, 36). Although some participants dropped out of school at the primary or secondary levels, 2 are currently enrolled in degree programmes at the Ambrose Ali University. All members of the group were literate, they could speak and write English clearly; thus, the discussion was held in English language. The focus group discussion was moderated by Precious and Iro. It lasted approximately 70 minutes and was audio-recorded and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

NGA3-D

This focus group discussion was held with 8 women in Ekpoma, Nigeria, in November 2021. Members of this group have weak ties to international migration: none had any international travel experience and most of them had no intention of travelling abroad. 2 participants were below 20 years, 3 above 30 years and 3 others in their twenties. Although they had varying levels of education, all could express themselves in either English and/or pidgin English. One participant was a full-time housewife, one was a farmer, 2 students, one civil servant and others were engaged in a few petty trades. The discussion was held in English and Pidgin English and was moderated by Precious and Dr. Iro. It lasted approximately one hour, 10 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated, and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK1-A

This focus group discussion was held with eight women in Chot Dheeran, Pakistan, in March 2020. All participants had someone in their household living abroad, though one of the women themselves had migrated. The participants ranged in age between 18 to 39. They included a teacher, housemaids, a university student, and women who are not in paid employment outside of their household. The discussion was held in Urdu and Punjabi and moderated by Safia Mahmood with assistant from Arslan Ahmad, while Furrukh Khan and Marta Bivand Erdal were also present. It lasted approximately 70 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK1-B

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in Chot Dheeran, Pakistan, in March 2020. All participants had very weak ties to migration, although one had a brother-in-law living abroad. The participants ranged in age from 20 to 39. They were of mixed education level, and worked as either teachers or were housewives. The discussion was held in Punjabi and moderated by Arslan Ahmad, with assistance from Safia Mahmood, while Marta Bivand Erdal and Furrukh Khan were also present. It lasted approximately 80 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK2-C

This focus group discussion was held with eight men in Chot Dheeran, Pakistan, in March 2020. The participants had generally weak ties to migration, but two of them did have a brother abroad. They were aged between 18 and 39. The participants worked in local government, the private sector, and civil society. The discussion was held in Punjabi and moderated by Arslan Ahmad, with assistance from Safia Mahmood, while Furrukh Khan and Marta Bivand Erdal were also present. It lasted approximately 90 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK1-D

This focus group discussion was held with nine men in Chot Dheeran, Pakistan in March 2020. All of the participants had either close family members abroad, or lived abroad themselves. The participants were aged between 20 and 39. Most of them had completed primary school education or beyond, and worked in farming, teaching and business. The discussion was held in Punjabi and moderated by Furrukh Khan with assistance from Arslan Ahmad, , while Marta Bivand Erdal and Safia Mahmood were also present. It lasted approximately 110 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK2-A

This focus group discussion was held with 6 women in Youhanabad, Pakistan, in November 2021. Participants mostly had relatives abroad. Some had husbands and brothers abroad, one of them had a sister working abroad, and one had lived for several years in another country in Asia. The group has people from 18-39 years old. 2 young women were formally attending schools, one of them was getting informal education and the others were not educated at all. The discussion was held in Punjabi & Urdu and moderated by Wardah Noor and Jovairiah while Marta Bivand Erdal was also present. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK2-B

This focus group discussion was held with six female in Youhanabad, Pakistan, in November 2021. The participants did not have immediate family members – household members – abroad. It turned out that one of them had her fiancée abroad. The participants ranged in age between 18 to 39. The discussion was held in Urdu, English, and Punjabi and moderated by Furrukh. A Khan and Wardah Noor while Marta Bivand Erdal and Jovairiah Batool were also present. It lasted approximately 45 minutes. It was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK2-C

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Youhanabad, Pakistan, in November 2021. All participants had someone in their household living abroad. The participants ranged in age between 18 to 39. One of them had only completed secondary education while all of the other members had some post-secondary education. Participants included a government hospital worker, a principal, and private sector worker. The discussion was held in Urdu, English, and Punjabi and moderated by Furrukh Khan, Arslan Ahmed and Wardah Noor while Marta Bivand Erdal was also present. It lasted approximately 90 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK2-D

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Youhanabad, Pakistan, in November 2021. All participants did not had immediate family members abroad except one whose brother was abroad. The participants ranged in age between 18 to 39. One of the participants completed his bachelors and preparing Civil Services exams while all the other participants are working. Two of them were working in Forman Christian College Lahore. One as a janitorial staff member and another one as Lab Assistant. The discussion was held in Urdu, English, and Punjabi and moderated by Furrukh. A Khan and Arslan Ahmad while Marta Bivand Erdal and other team members Behroz Karim, Jovairiah Batool, Wardah Noor, and Aneeb Ul Hassan were also present. It lasted approximately one hour and ten minutes. It was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK3-A

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Keti Bandar, Pakistan, in July 2021. The participants all had weak ties with migration, with no close relatives who had left or moved to this area. The women were all between 18-29 years old. Most of the women in this group were occupied with housework, however, some of them also ran businesses from their homes, one was studying, another a health worker. The discussion was held in Sindhi and moderated by Rashid Memon, assisted by Neha Ramchand. It lasted approximately 1 hour and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK3-B

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Keti Bandar, Pakistan in July 2021. The participants had strong migration ties, with five of six themselves having migrated to Keti Bandar for employment reasons. The participants were in their 20s and 30s. They were all working, but unlike most locals who were engaged in fisheries, the participants worked in trade, one as a farmer, and another as a teacher. The discussion was held in Sindhi and Urdu and moderated by Furrukh Khan with the assistance of Sehr Nisar. It lasted approximately 1 hour and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK3-C

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Keti Bandar, Pakistan, in July 2021 with weak migration links. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 39, with three in their 20s. They included fishers, as well as one man who was a shop keeper and another who did not have a job. The discussion was held in Sindhi and in Urdu and moderated by Furrukh Khan, with assistance from Sehr Nisar. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

PAK3-D

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Keti Bandar, Pakistan, in July 2021. The group's participants all had strong links with migration, whose family members had migrated or they themselves had migration experience (internal within Pakistan). These women were between 18-39 years old. Most of the women in this group were occupied with housework, however, some of them also ran businesses from their homes. The discussion was held in Sindhi and moderated by Rashid Memon, assisted by Neha Ramchand. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM1-A

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Erigavo, Somaliland (former North Somalia), in June 2021. All participants had mentioned that they always lived in the country and had no close relatives who lived abroad. [They were between the ages of 30 and 39s except one who has much younger. Most of them didn't finish primary school. The discussion was held in Somali and moderated by Fatuma and Ahmed Omer. It lasted approximately one hour and 12 minutes and was audio recorded and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM1-B

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Erigavo, Somaliland (former North Somalia) in June 2021. The group had either a close family member living abroad or they themselves returned after working or studying outside of Erigavo. Most of them had no formal school education and some were involved in small business, while the others were housewives or were unemployed. The discussion was held in Somali and moderated by Fatuma and Ahmed. It lasted approximately 60 minutes and was audio-recorded and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM1-C

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Erigavo, in August 2021. All participants lived in Erigavo, Somaliland (former North Somalia) and know the expectation of daily lives in Erigavo for the past and present. Most of them completed primary education. The discussion lasted approximately 1 hour and 20 minutes and participants expressed their thoughts on the topic. The age ranges among the participants were middle 20s and the beginning of 30s. Participants were careful not to talk about personal opinions but kept the discussion on more general terms despite being reassured of anonymity. The discussion was audio-recorded and translated transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM1-D

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Erigavo, Somaliland (former North Somalia), in June 2021. All participants had mentioned that they always lived in the country and had no close relatives who lived abroad. They were between the ages of 20 and 35s. Most of them had no formal school education. The discussion was held in Somali and moderated by Fatuma and Ahmed Omer. It lasted approximately one hour and was audio recorded and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM2-A

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Baidoa, Somalia, in April 2021. The group all had direct migration experience, either as IDPs, refugee returnees, or in-migrants from Ethiopia and Kenya (of Somali descent). Three of the women were in their early to mid-twenties, and three were in their early thirties. The two in-migrants (Ethiopian and Kenyan Somali) had completed post-secondary education; none of the other women had completed any schooling. The discussion was held in Somali May and moderated by Gedi Ahmed, with Camille Kasavan and Fatuma Ahmed present and intervening on some questions. It lasted approximately 100 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM2-B

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Baidoa, Somalia in April 2021. The group included two refugee returnees from Kenya, one IDP, and one in-migrant who had original ties to the research area. Two were in their mid-twenties and two in their early thirties. The group had all completed secondary education. The discussion was held in Maay (local dialect) and moderated by Gedi Ahmed, in the presence of Fatuma Ahmed and Camille Kasavan. It lasted approximately 120 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM2-C

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Baidoa, Somalia, in April 2021. The group were all women with Baidoa, with one woman who had moved to Baidoa from a surrounding rural area for marriage. Two of the women had distant relatives abroad; the rest had no relatives abroad. Most of the women were in their early to mid-twenties, with one in her late thirties. Two of the women had no education at all, while three had high school or post-secondary education. The discussion was held in Maay (local dialect) and moderated by Gedi Ahmed, in the presence of Fatuma Ahmed and Camille Kasavan. It lasted approximately 90 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

SOM2-D

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Baidoa, Somalia, in April 2021. The men were all from Baidoa and did not have family abroad. They were mainly in their mid-twenties, and one was in his early thirties. All had completed high school. The discussion was held in Maay (local dialect) and moderated by Gedi Ahmed, in the presence of Fatuma Ahmed and Camille Kasavan. It lasted approximately 115 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN1-A

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Enfidha, Tunisia, in February 2021. All participants had close family members abroad (parent or sibling) and one had direct international migration experience. The participants were in their early 20s to mid-30s. All of them had completed secondary school and one had some university education. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic, with translation from French and moderated by Safouen Azouzi and Camille Kasavan. It lasted approximately 90 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN1-B

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Enfidha, Tunisia in February 2021. None of the men had immediate family members abroad, although some knew people who had gone aboard. Participants were mainly in their late 20s, with some in their early 30s. [One or two sentences on the group's level of education and current activities.] The discussion was held in [language] and moderated by [name (s)/ name (s) and an interpreter]. It lasted approximately [number rounded to the nearest 10] minutes and was [audio-recorded and translated and transcribed/recorded by means of note-taking]. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN1-C

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Enfidha, in February 2021. The women had no direct relatives abroad. The women were mainly in their early to mid-30s, with two in their late 20s. All the women except for one had some post-secondary education; all had finished high school. Most were housewives, although many had unpaid volunteer or community activities outside of the home as well. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic and moderated by Camille Kasavan and Safouen Azouzi, with the latter translating as well. It lasted approximately 70 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN1-D

This focus group discussion was held with four women in Enfidha, Tunisia, in February 2021. All the women had an immediate relative who had migrated abroad (mainly brothers, and in one instance the participants' father). All of the women had post-secondary education – three were housewives who were also engaged in community and volunteer activities, and the fourth worked in a translation office in Enfidha. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic and moderated by Camille Kasavan and Safouen Azouzi, with the latter translating as well. It lasted approximately 100 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN2-A

This focus group discussion was held with four men in Redeyef, Tunisia in March 2021. One of the group members had actual migration experience (to Europe); all the others had at least one brother abroad (all in Europe). Participants were all in their mid to late 30s, except for one in his early 20s. All participants had at least completed secondary education, and two had some post-secondary education as well; they included an electrician, a cybercafe employee who was also a university student, a daily labourer, and one who was unemployed and took on occasional daily work. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic, with translations or interjections in French, and moderated by Camille Kasavan and Safouen Azouzi, with the latter taking an active translation role and asking follow up questions independently where needed. It lasted approximately 100 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN2-B

This focus group discussion was held with seven men in Redeyef, Tunisia in March 2021. Group members had no migration experience and no immediate (siblings or brothers) family abroad, although nearly all except for one had extended family (cousins, uncle) abroad. The group included a mix of men in their mid-late 30s and mid-20s, as well as one 19 year old. Four of the group were unemployed/supporting themselves through occasional daily labour, one was a senior high school student and two owned small businesses. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic with translation in French – nearly all participants spoke a basic level of French (some more) and would make occasional interjections in French, although the bulk of the discussion was in Tunisian Arabic. This was moderated by Camille Kasavan and Safouen Azouzi, with the latter taking an active translation role and asking follow up questions independently where needed. It lasted approximately 110 minutes and was audio-recorded, translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN2-C

This focus group discussion was held with four women in Redeyef, Tunisia in March 2021. Participants did not have any immediate family abroad, although some had cousins or knew neighbours who had migrated. The group was young, with two of the participants in the 18-19 age range, one 20 year old, and another woman in her mid-20s. All the women had at least finished high school, and two were currently university students, while one had graduated university. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic with some French interjections and moderated by Camille Kasavan and Safouen Azouzi, with the latter taking an active translation role and asking follow up questions independently where needed. It lasted approximately 120 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUN2-D

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Redeyef, Tunisia in March 2021. All of the participants had at least one sibling abroad, and in some cases participants had several siblings or other relatives abroad. The group was evenly split between women in their mid/late 20s and women in their early 30s. All of the women had completed high school, and half of them also had at least some post-secondary education (with two having completed their degrees completely). The group included three small business owners, one housewife, and two women who worked part time in varying roles, including as a sports coach and with community organisations. The discussion was held in Tunisian Arabic and moderated by Camille Kasavan and Safouen Azouzi, with the latter taking an active translation role and asking follow up questions independently where needed. It lasted approximately 90 minutes and was audio-recorded and translated and transcribed. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR1-A

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Hopa, Turkey, in August 2021. Four participants do not have family members/relatives or close friends abroad. Two of them have relatives abroad, but they do not have regular communication/contact. The participants ranged in age between 19 and 36. One participant was a high school student; the rest were educated at secondary level or above. The participants included two university students, one journalist, one teacher, and one seasonal worker. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pinar Ensari. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR1-B

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in Hopa, Turkey, in August 2021. All participants had family members/relatives and/or friends abroad with whom they are in regular contact. The participants ranged in age between 24 and 31. All participants were university graduates except for one who was a university student. They included an architect, one housewife, two teachers, one lawyer, and a university student. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pinar Ensari. It lasted approximately 1 hours 40 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR1-C

This focus group discussion was held with five men in Hopa, Turkey, in August 2021. Participants had family members/relatives and/or friends abroad with whom they were in regular contact. The participants ranged in age between 19 to 36. The participants were educated at secondary level or above. They included a restaurant owner, an electrician, an engineer, a teacher, and a university student. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pinar Ensari. It lasted approximately 2 hours and 10 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR1-D

This focus group discussion was held with six women in Hopa, Turkey, in August 2021. Five participants had relatives abroad, yet they were not in regular contact. One participant did not have any family member or relative abroad. The participants ranged in age between 21 and 39. They included two teachers, two university students, a salesclerk, and a manager. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Pınar Ensari with assistance from Nilay Kavur. It lasted approximately 1 hours and 40 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR2-A

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in Yenice, Turkey, in July 2021. All participants had a background in another city. They either migrated from another city to Yenice, or currently studying at university in another city, or finished university at another city and migrated back to Yenice. The participants ranged in age between 21 to 39. They were educated at secondary level or above. The participants included an architect, a cook, an entrepreneur, an accountant, two university students, and one unemployed. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pınar Ensari. It lasted approximately 2 hours and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR2-B

This focus group discussion was held with nine women in Yenice, Turkey, in July 2021. All participants had a background in another city, except for one who strongly desires to go to university in another city in Turkey and live there. The rest either migrated from another city to Yenice or finished university at another city and migrated back to Yenice. The participants ranged in age between 18 to 38. They included three factory workers, three teachers, one student, one civil servant, and cook/husbandman. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pınar Ensari. It lasted approximately 1 hours 50 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR2-C

This focus group discussion was held with five women in Yenice, Turkey, in July 2021. None of the participants lived outside of Çanakkale. Three of them did not even live outside of Yenice. The participants ranged in age between 22 to 36. They included a health worker (intern), a pharmacy technician, a factory forewoman, a security guard, and a clerk. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Pınar Ensari with assistance from Nilay Kavur. It lasted approximately 2 hours and 5 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR2-D

This focus group discussion was held with six men in Yenice, Turkey, in July 2021. None of the participants lived outside of Yenice. Two of them migrated from Yenice's villages to the district center. The participants ranged in age between 25 to 39. They included an accountant, a security guard, a civil servant, a manual worker, a civil servant/husbandman, and a pharmacy technician. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pınar Ensari, while Ahmet İçduygu was also present. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR3-A

This focus group discussion was held with seven women in Kilis, Turkey in September 2021. All participants were Turkish women. The participants ranged in age from 20 to 36. They included university students, a teacher, an education consultant, a housewife, and one who runs a psychotechnics centre. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Nilay Kavur with assistance from Pınar Ensari. It lasted approximately 2 hours and 45 minutes, and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR3-B

This focus group discussion was held with 5 men in Kilis, Turkey, in September 2021. All participants were Turkish men. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 33. The participants were educated at secondary level or above. They included engineer, driver, teacher, university student and civil servant, and a seller in the bazaar. The discussion was held in Turkish and moderated by Pınar Ensari with assistance from Nilay Kavur. It lasted approximately 1 hour 36 minutes, and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR3-C

This focus group discussion was held with 8 women in Kilis, Turkey, in September 2021. All participants were Syrian women who came from Syria to Turkey after 2011. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 39. They included housewives, a university student, a midwife, and a young woman who recently finished high school and was preparing for university entrance exams. The discussion was mostly held in Arabic. However, one participant preferred to speak in Turkish, yet she could also follow conversations in Arabic. The discussion in Arabic was moderated by Souad Osseiran, and the discussion in Turkish was moderated by Pınar Ensari. It lasted approximately 1 hour 55 minutes, and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.

TUR3-D

This focus group discussion was held with 7 men in Kilis, Turkey, in September 2021. All participants were Syrian men who came from Syria to Turkey after 2011. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 32. They included a tradesman/translator, a medical translator, a university student/prosthetic technician, an unemployed, and those working in the customs sector and car trading. The discussion was held in Arabic and moderated by Ayman Abousamra while Nilay Kavur was also present. It lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated. Information that could directly or indirectly identify participants has been removed.